

FeCl₃ catalyzed tandem synthesis of optically pure sugar based benzimidazoles

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A chemo-selective synthesis of optically pure sugar based benzimidazole from reaction of glycol-2-carboxaldehyde and *ortho*-phenylene diamine by FeCl₃ catalyzed tandem imination, cyclisation followed by green oxidation by aerial O₂ is reported. Some selected tailor-made chiral benzimidazoles were screened for antimicrobial activity against clinically isolated drug-resistant bacteria, as well as fungi obtained from superficial dermal infections.

Keywords: FeCl₃, catalyzed, glycol, benzimidazole, tandem.

Introduction

The importance of nitrogen-containing heterocycles originates from their wide occurrence in Nature and broad application in chemistry, biology, and material sciences¹. The most prominent benzimidazole (BZM) compound in Nature is *N*-ribosyl 5,6-dimethylbenzimidazole which serves as an axial ligand for cobalt in Vitamin B12^{2a} and has generated considerable interest in the area of BZM based nucleoside and nucleotides or the corresponding analogs^{2b-e}.

BZM and its derivatives are widespread in many therapeutic areas and have versatile pharmacological properties³ such as antiviral^{3a}, (Hep.C, HIV), antibacterial^{3b}, antifungal^{3c}, antitumor^{3d}, antihelminthics^{3e}, etc. BZMs have importance as analgesic^{3f} or cardiovascular agents^{3g} and are useful in neuroresearch^{3h}, endocrinology³ⁱ and also in ophthalmology^{3j}. Apart from these the antiallergic^{3k} and antihistaminic^{3l} activity of compounds containing BZM moiety have also been reported. BZM frameworks are also finding many applications in several other fields⁴.

The BZM motif occurs in many approved and investigational drugs (Fig. 1)⁵. Some established drugs like

omeprazole, pantoprazole, lansoprazole, dexlansoprazole (dexillant-enantiomer of lansoprazole, Fig. 1) and esomeprazole (nexium, Fig. 1) are also having common benzimidazole sulfoxide framework and are used as proton pump inhibitors (PPIs)⁶ in mammals, especially in human beings.

Fig. 1. Drugs containing chiral benzimidazole frameworks.

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Many synthetic nucleosides^{2b-e,3f,7} and nucleotides^{2b-e} of BZM are known. Structurally diverse molecules having novel skeletons are of primal requirement for drug discovery. Development of improved synthetic methodologies, particularly tandem ones⁸ involving multiple chemical transformations in one-pot by a single catalyst, is of immense importance for generation of library compounds. The transition metal catalyzed cycloisomerisation approach is a powerful tool for the assembly of diverse heterocyclic frameworks⁹. Over the past few years, iron salts¹⁰ have emerged as promising catalysts and thus have attracted increasing research interest of chemists. Due to the low price, non-toxicity, ready availability and environmentally friendly character recently, particularly FeCl₃ has received much attention in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds^{10a,c,11}. In connection to our work on synthesis of heterocycles¹² and also on glycal systems¹³, we report herein chemo-selective synthesis of chiral benzimidazoles by cyclocondensation of OPDs (*o*-phenylene diamines) with tri-*O*-benzyl/methyl glycal-2-carboxaldehydes by FeCl₃ catalyzed tandem imination, cyclisation and aerial oxidation in refluxing CH₃CN in one-pot (Table 1, Schemes 1 and 2) along with the results of antimicrobial assays of some selected chiral benzimidazoles (Tables 2-4 and Fig. 4-7).

Results and discussion

SiO₂-FeCl₃/H₂O₂^{14a}, sulfonic acid functionalized imidazolium salts-FeCl₃^{14b}, I₂ alone or in combination with other reagents^{14c,d} and ZrOCl₂.8H₂O^{14e} are known to form

benzimidazoles from reaction of aldehydes and *o*-phenylenediamines. Of these I₂^{15a}, and FeCl₃^{15b}, and other catalyst like InCl₃^{15c}, are reported to give *O*- or -C Ferrier rearrangements in glycals. Benzimidazole as well as benzodiazepine is generated by FeCl₃ catalyzed oxidative condensation of α,β -unsaturated aldehyde (cinnamaldehyde) and *o*-phenylene diamine (our unpublished observation). InCl₃ is also known to catalyze the synthesis of sugar derived 1,5-benzodiazepine from reaction of sugar derived α,β -unsaturated- δ -hydroxyaldehyde (non-glycal system) and *o*-phenylenediamine^{15d}.

Initially, we were thus in search of a suitable reagent or reagent system that would not cause direct Ferrier type rearrangement in the 3,4,6-tri-*O*-benzyl-D-glucal-2-carboxaldehyde (**1a**) by *o*-phenylenediamine (**2a**) but could generate preferably either benzimidazole or benzodiazepines through reaction of the initially formed imine intermediate **I** by attack of the other free amino group on the imino carbon [pathway (a)] or on the anomeric carbon [pathway (b) or (c)], respectively, followed by oxidation (Scheme 1). With this end in view, 3,4,6-tri-*O*-benzyl-glucal-2-carboxaldehyde (**1a**) was reacted separately with (**2a**) in the presence of several catalysts like InCl₃, La(OTf)₃, ZrOCl₂.8H₂O, I₂ and FeCl₃ under different reaction conditions. The best yield of the corresponding optically pure benzimidazole (**3a**, 90%) was obtained by refluxing a mixture of **1a** and **2a** in CH₃CN in the presence of 20 mol% FeCl₃(Table 1). Neither the corresponding benzodiazepines **4a** or **5a** nor any dialkylated benzimidazole **6a** could be traced out in the crude product. Thus, here the condi-

Scheme 1. Probable anticipated pathways.

Table 1. FeCl₃ catalyzed one-pot synthesis of library of glycal fused chiral benzimidazoles
^aSee Fig. 2 for the structure of products

Entry	Glycal aldehyde	OPD	Product	Time	Yield	Nature/m.p.
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(h)	(%)	(°C)
1	1a	2a	3a ^{7f}	6	90	Solid/110
2	1a	2b	3b ^{7f}	8	81	Foam
3	1a	2c	3c ^{7f}	8	78	Foam
4	1a	2d	3d	6.5	85	Foam
5	1a	2e	3e	7	81	Foam
6	1a	2f	3f	10	77	Foam
7	1a	2g	3g ^{7f}	11	76	Solid/126
8	1b	2a	3h ^{7f}	6	82	Syrup
9	1b	2c	3i	7	70	Syrup
10	1b	2d	3j	6	81	Syrup
11	1b	2e	3k	5	70	Syrup
12	1b	2g	3l ^{7f}	12	71	Solid/289–291
13	1c	2a	3m ^{7f}	7	80	Syrup
14	1c	2c	3n	7	48	Syrup
15	1c	2e	3o	7	78	Syrup
16	1c	2f	3p ^{7f}	11	78	Foam
17	1c	2g	3q ^{7f}	14	71	Solid/166
18	1d	2g	3r ^{7f}	10	80	Solid/236

^aAll reactions were performed by using 1.0 equiv. of aldehyde, 1.5 equiv. of *ortho*-phenylenediamine and 20% of FeCl₃ in CH₃CN under reflux condition; the yields reported in the table are the isolated yields of the compounds.

tion is highly chemoselective. It is worthy to mention here that Maiti *et al.*^{7f} have also reported recently the synthesis of benzimidazoles (including chiral ones) from reactions of aldehydes including glycal derived aldehydes and *o*-phenylenediamines based on VO(acac)₂-CeCl₃-Ti(OBu)₄ Combo catalyst. We have proved unequivocally the structure of the sugar-based benzimidazole **3a** by XRD analysis¹⁶ (CCDC No. 905529) (Fig. 3a) and NMR (¹H and ¹³C, 1D and 2D) analysis. This result incited us to further explore

this methodology towards synthesis of diversified optically pure benzimidazole scaffolds.

Under the standard reaction condition, various glycal-2-carboxaldehydes **1(a-d)** in reaction with *o*-phenylenediamine **2a** or its analogs **2(b-g)** generated the corresponding optically pure benzimidazoles (**3**, Table 1) in good to excellent yields (70–90%). Corresponding benzodiazepines or bis-sugar derivatives were not formed in any of these cases. 3,4,6-Tri-O-benzyl-D-glucal-2-carboxaldehyde (**1a**) in reac-

Fig. 2 Structure of glycal fused chiral benzimidazole products.

tion with *o*-phenylenediamines containing substituents having +I effect **2b** and **2c** or having –I and +R effects **2d** or –I, –R effects **2e** and **2f** afforded the corresponding benzimidazoles **3b–3f** in high yields (77–85%). Similarly, 3,4,6-tri-*O*-methyl-glucal-2-carboxaldehyde **1b** also reacted efficiently under the optimized condition with **2a** and **2c–2e** furnishing the corresponding optically pure benzimidazoles (**3h** and **3i–3k**) in good yields (70–82%). The efficacy of the present procedure was further proved from the reaction of *O*-benzylated galactal-2-carboxaldehyde **1c** with **2a**, **2c** or its electron deficient analogs (**2e** and **2f**), which uniformly generated the corresponding optically pure benzimidazoles **3m**, **3o** and **3p** respectively in high yields (78–80%) [except **3n**, that was obtained in moderate yield]. The applicability of the present method was further explored for synthesis of sugar based benzimidazoles from reactions of aldehydes (**1a–1d**) with 1,2-diamino-9,10-anthraquinone **2g** which gave the corresponding desired optically pure products, **3g**, **3l**, **3q** and **3r**, respectively in quite high yields (71–80%). In general the rate of reactions of 4-benzoyl-*o*-phenylenediamine **2f** or the *o*-diaminoquinone **2g** were slower (reaction time: 10–14 h) in comparison with those of the other *o*-diaminoaromatic compounds (5–8 h). It is also to be noted that all the reactions under Table 1 were clean and high yielding compared to those

Fig. 3. (a) Crystal structure (ORTEP diagram) of compound **3a**, (b) crystal structure of compound **3l**.

reported earlier^{7f}. We also want to mention that the structure and the stability of the specific tautomeric form **3i** has been confirmed unequivocally by XRD analysis¹⁶, CCDC No. 905528 (Fig. 3b) of its single crystal.

It is interesting to note that *o*-phenylenediamine **2b** or **2d** containing Me or Cl group at C-4 in reaction with sugar aldehydes generated in all cases the corresponding 5-methyl- or 5-chloro-benzimidazoles (Table 1). On the other hand, *o*-phenylenediamine analogues containing electron withdrawing groups (-I, -R) such as -NO₂ or -COPh at C-4 (**2e** or **2f**) reacted with the glycal-2-carboxaldehydes affording the corresponding 6-NO₂- or 6-benzoylbenzimidazoles.

The plausible mechanistic pathway for the formation of compounds (**3**) is depicted in Scheme 2. The reaction is most probably initiated by FeCl₃ catalyzed formation of the intermediate Schiff's base **I**, which in its *s-trans* form can proceed via formation of a 6-membered chelate through coordination of Fe(III) with imine N and C₃-O of the glycal moiety,

eventually producing the corresponding dihydrobenzimidazole intermediate **II**. **II** is finally oxidized *in situ* by Fe(III) catalyzed oxidation where aerial O₂ plays the key role as shown in the inset of Scheme 2.

The most important point to be noted is that just refluxing of the reaction mixture using a guard tube can produce the benzimidazole products (**3**) in high yields. Continuous flow (or bubbling) of O₂ is not necessary for the oxidation step (as this does not increase the yield of products).

That O₂ plays the key role and the oxidation is mediated by Fe(III) are also evidenced from the fact that the reaction fails to give any product in the absence of FeCl₃, and also that a small amount of the desired product is obtained when a reaction was performed under N₂-atmosphere.

As has been mentioned earlier benzimidazoles are considered as a promising class of bioactive heterocyclic compounds exhibiting a wide range of biological activities³. Benzimidazole urea, discovered by the use of structure-guided

Scheme 2. Proposed mechanism for the synthesis of **3a**.

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of the synthesized benzimidazole derivatives on microorganisms isolated from skin and subcutaneous infection

Microorganism; Source	Inhibition zones of microbial growth (mm) ^a										MIC values (µg/ml)									
	Benzimidazole derivatives (0.2 mg/well)					Standard drugs (0.02 mg/well)					Benzimidazole derivatives									
	3a	3c	3o	3n	3l	3g	3r	3f	C	G	F	3a	3c	3o	3n	3l	3g	3r		
Gram-positive bacteria:																				
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (MSSA);	B	7	9	b	9	8	10	16	16	ND	ND	>512	256	128	>512	128	256	128		
Vaginal swab																				
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (MRSA);	6	b	7	b	B	8	B	22	16	ND	ND	>512	>512	256	>512	>512	256	>512		
Wound swab:																				
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i> ;	8	8	B	6	7	10	8	24	22	ND	ND	256	256	>512	256	256	128	256		
Pus																				
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> ;	B	b	7	b	B	6	8	10	19	ND	ND	>512	>512	256	>512	>512	256	256		
Pus																				
Gram-negative bacteria																				
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ESBL producer);	B	6	6	b	B	7	8	9	16	ND	ND	>512	256	>512	>512	>512	256	256		
Vaginal swab:																				
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (ESBL producer);	B	6	b	b	B	10	7	10	16	ND	ND	>512	256	>512	>512	>512	128	256		
Wound swab																				
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i> (ESBL non-producer);	7	b	8	6	8	9	B	26	22	ND	ND	>512	256	256	128	256	>512	>512		
Wound swab																				
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> ;	B	b	8	7	9	6	B	22	18	ND	ND	>512	256	256	128	256	>512	>512		
Pus																				
Fungal strains:																				
<i>Candida albicans</i> ;	7	8	6	9	8	6	10	ND	ND	18	18	256	256	>512	256	256	>512	128		
Skin scraping																				
<i>Candida tropicalis</i> ;	10	11	B	15	11	9	12	ND	ND	14	14	128	128	>512	128	128	128	128		
Pus																				

^aIncluding diameter of well (5 mm). "b": No activity. ND: Not Determined. "C": Ciprofloxacin. "G": Gentamicin. "F": Fluconazole, MSSA: methicillin sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus*, MRSA: methicillin resistance *S. aureus*, ESBL: extended spectrum β-lactamase.

design and structure-activity relationships, was found to be dual targeting inhibitors of DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV, with potent antibacterial activity against a wide spectrum of relevant pathogens responsible for hospital- and community-acquired infections¹⁷. In the present study, seven benzimidazole derivatives were selected for prospective antimicrobial assessment. Bacterial and fungal isolates were taken from patients suffering with superficial and subcutaneous infections, constituting four Gram-positive, four Gram-negative and a two *Candida* spp. (Table 2). The collected bacterial strains, when tested for their antibiotic resistance profile, were found to be resistant against multiple antibiotics (Table 3). One of the bacteria was methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and two of the Gram-negative bacilli were extended spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) producers¹⁸, which are currently posing global problem in clinical therapeutics due to their multi-drug resistant characteristics.

In the present study, the compound **3g** responded, more or less, to all the tested organisms, while the other six compounds exhibited 'mild' to 'no activity' against the bacterial strains (Table 2, Fig. 4). However, all the compounds responded positively to both the *Candida* spp. (Table 2, Fig. 5). The MIC determined for the compounds showed the lowest value at 128 μ g/ml (Table 2). The tested dose of 200 μ g/well, although 10-fold higher than the standard drugs, would be compatible for dermal medication regimens, particularly for treatment of fungal diseases, since the test organisms were isolated from superficial and subcutaneous infections. Hence, the selected benzimidazoles might be developed for prospective therapeutic application against candidiasis.

Invasive fungal infections have become major causes of morbidity and mortality among immune-suppressed patients. *Candida* species are now a frequent cause of nosocomial blood stream infections in critically ill patients even in developed countries¹⁹. Therefore, we decided to further investigate the extent of DNA damage in *Candida tropicalis* following treatment with two of the derivatives (**3n** and **3r**) by using alkaline comet assay. The study was done in terms of migrated DNA fragments by using fifteen commonly used parameters, taking hydrogen peroxide as a standard control. Interestingly, we detected increased levels of DNA fragmentation in fungal cells treated with benzimidazoles as compared with the untreated (negative control) cells ($p < 0.05$)

Fig. 4. Antibacterial activity of benzimidazole derivatives viz. (i) **3a**, (ii) **3c**, (iii) **3o**, (iv) **3n**, (v) **3l**, (vi) **3g** and (vii) **3r** against *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA), (viii) Ciprofloxacin and (ix) gentamicin, at 0.02 mg/well, were used as positive controls and 50 μ L DMSO was used as (x) vehicle control.

Table 3. *In vitro* antibiotic resistance pattern of the clinically isolated bacteria

Bacteria	Specimen	Antibiotic resistance
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (MSSA)	Vaginal swab	E, Nx, Ca, Cfm
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (MRSA)	Wound swab	Cfx, Nx, Pt, Ca, cfm, Cf
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	Pus	Ca, Cfm, V, Cl
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	Pus	As, Amc, Cp, Cfx, Cip, Lv, Nx, Of, Sfx
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ESBL producer)	Vaginal swab	Cfx, Cip, Nx, Sfx, Ca
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (ESBL producer)	Wound swab	As, Amc, Cfx, Cip, Cl, Nx, Of, Pt, Sfx, Ca, Cfm, Cfs, Ao
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i> (ESBL non-producer)	Wound swab	Do, Ca
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Pus	As, Amc, Cl, Do, Cfm, Ao

MSSA: methicillin sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus*, MRSA: methicillin resistance *S. aureus*, ESBL: extended spectrum β -lactamase, As: Ampicillin/Sulbactam (10/10 μ g), Amc: Amoxy-Clavulanic acid (20/10 μ g), Ao: Aztreonam (30 μ g), Ca: Ceftazidime (30 μ g), Cfm: Cefixime (5 μ g), Cfs: Cefoperazone/Sulbactam (75/30 μ g), Cf: Cefoxitin (30 μ g), Cp: Cephalexin (30 μ g), Cfx: Cefuroxime (30 μ g), Cip: Ciprofloxacin (5 μ g), Cl: Ceftriaxone (30 μ g), Do: Doxycycline (30 μ g), E: Erythromycin (30 μ g), Lv: Levofloxacin (5 μ g), Nx: Norfloxacin (10 μ g), Of: Ofloxacin (5 μ g), Pt: Piperacillin/Tazobactam (100/10 μ g), Sfx: Sparfloxacin (5 μ g), V: Vancomycin (30 μ g).

Table 4. Evaluation of DNA damaging effect of the synthesized benzimidazole derivatives on *Candida tropicalis* by Comet assay

	Negative control Mean±SE ^a	3n Treated Mean±SE (p-value ^b)	3r Treated Mean±SE (p-value)	Positive control Mean±SE (p-value)
Comet length (μm)	2.72±0.07	4.50±0.15 (1.59×10 ⁻¹¹)	4.69±0.22 (4.04×10 ⁻⁹)	6.85±0.36 (8.57×10 ⁻¹¹)
Comet height (μm)	2.93±0.06	3.76±0.11 (8.63×10 ⁻⁸)	3.60±0.09 (7.04×10 ⁻⁷)	3.71±0.14 (1.22×10 ⁻⁵)
Comet area (μm ²)	7.80±0.28	15.49±0.72 (1.38×10 ⁻¹⁰)	15.73±1.06 (1.82×10 ⁻⁷)	22.62±1.95 (1.65×10 ⁻⁷)
Comet intensity	10257.23±267.42	14044.18±1138.03 (3.58×10 ⁻³)	14253.32±1590.77 (2.13×10 ⁻²)	20265.41±1962.47 (4.77×10 ⁻⁵)
Comet mean intensity	76.45±3.13	50.95±3.29 (1.43×10 ⁻⁶)	48.97±2.81 (7.19×10 ⁻⁸)	49.80±2.24 (3.18×10 ⁻⁸)
Head diameter (μm)	2.61±0.09	3.20±0.15 (1.34×10 ⁻³)	2.79±0.19 (0.39)	3.42±0.29 (1.24×10 ⁻²)
Head area (μm ²)	7.71±0.27	13.23±0.76 (3.04×10 ⁻⁷)	14.09±1.03 (3.83×10 ⁻⁶)	14.19±1.60 (6.01×10 ⁻⁴)
Head mean intensity	72.96±3.17	41.45±2.27 (8.95×10 ⁻¹⁰)	35.56±2.75 (3.74×10 ⁻¹¹)	41.31±3.32 (2.11×10 ⁻⁸)
%DNA in head	94.65±1.84	70.38±3.11 (1.03×10 ⁻⁷)	64.52±3.91 (9.68×10 ⁻⁸)	52.39±5.28 (5.040×10 ⁻⁸)
Tail length (μm)	0.21±0.06	1.30±0.13 (2.69×10 ⁻⁸)	1.89±0.22 (8.98×10 ⁻⁸)	3.43±0.30 (3.12×10 ⁻¹⁰)
Tail area (μm ²)	0.09±0.02	2.26±0.33 (1.45×10 ⁻⁶)	1.65±0.29 (2.05×10 ⁻⁵)	8.43±1.39 (6.09×10 ⁻⁶)
Tail intensity	573.45±197.95	4295.41±637.95 (8.54×10 ⁻⁶)	4834.45±810.80 (3.38×10 ⁻⁵)	9549.27±1252.65 (4.18×10 ⁻⁷)
% DNA in tail	5.35±1.84	29.62±3.11 (1.03×410 ⁻⁷)	35.48±3.91 (9.68×10 ⁻⁸)	47.61±5.28 (5.04×10 ⁻⁸)
Tail moment	0.06±0.03	1.70±0.27 (3.77×10 ⁻⁶)	3.16±0.59 (3.13×10 ⁻⁵)	7.70±1.13 (1.05×10 ⁻⁶)
Olive moment	0.17±0.06	1.55±0.17 (5.07×10 ⁻⁸)	2.04±0.25 (2.00×10 ⁻⁷)	5.12±0.65 (1.52×10 ⁻⁷)

^aSE: Standard error. ^bp-value is the result of comparison with negative control by independent, two tailed, Studentt-test. p < 0.05 is considered as statistically significant.

(Table 4 and Fig. 6). Among the fifteen calculated comet assay parameters, tail length, tail intensity, % DNA in tail, and tail moment were depicted in box-whisker plots, for the visual comparison between untreated control, 3n-treated, 3r-treated, and hydrogen peroxide treated fungal cells (Fig. 7). DNA damage may result in apoptosis or induction of mutations which are believed to be the mode of antifungal activity of this class of heterocyclic compounds.

In fact, there are very few reports on comet assay per-

formed for the assessment of drug-induced DNA fragmentation in *Candida* spp.²⁰, and to the best of our knowledge, the present study is one of the first such works published on benzimidazoles.

Conclusion

In summary, we have demonstrated an efficient chemoselective clean tandem synthesis of sugar based optically pure benzimidazoles from reactions of glycal-2-

Fig. 5. Antifungal activity of benzimidazole derivatives viz. (i) **3a**, (ii) **3c**, (iii) **3o**, (iv) **3n**, (v) **3l**, (vi) **3g** and (vii) **3r** against *Candida tropicalis*. (viii) Fluconazole (0.02 mg/well) was used as positive control and 50 μ L DMSO was used as (ix) vehicle control.

Fig. 6. Extent of DNA damage in *Candida tropicalis*. (A) Untreated fungal cells; (B) 100 μ L hydrogen peroxide treated fungal cells; (C) **3n** (200 μ g/ml) treated fungal cells; (D) **3r** (200 μ g/ml) treated fungal cells.

Fig. 7. Box-whisker plot (graphical representation of the smallest observation, lower quartile, median, upper quartile, and largest observation) showing comparison between untreated control, **3n** (200 μ g/ml) treated, **3r** (200 μ g/ml) treated, and 100 μ L hydrogen peroxide treated fungal cells (positive control) for (A) Tail length, (B) Tail intensity, (C) %DNA in tail and (D) Tail moment treated fungal cells.

carboxaldehydes and *o*-arylenediamines in the presence of FeCl₃ catalyst and aerial O₂ as the green oxidant. Screening of some selected optically pure benzimidazoles for their antibacterial and antifungal activities using drug resistant clinical isolates was performed, and comet assay of two such selected compounds against *Candida tropicalis* afforded promising results for prospective consideration of these two compounds for dermal application.

Experimental

General:

All commercially available reagents were used directly without further purification unless otherwise stated. All reactions were conducted under atmospheric O₂ (air) unless otherwise stated. Acetonitrile for reaction was dried and distilled prior to use according to standard method (dried over calcium chloride and phosphorus pentachloride). Product purification by column chromatography was accomplished using silica gel (60–120 mesh). Technical grade solvents were used for chromatography and distilled prior to use. Melting points were uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on BX-II FT-IR spectrometer in KBr with absorptions in wavenumbers (cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR of the products were determined on Bruker DPX-300 spectrometer at ambient temperature in CDCl₃. *J* values are in hertz (Hz). Chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in parts per million (ppm). High Resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were obtained by a Q-tof-Micro (YA-263) mass spectrometer by electron spray ionization method.

Single crystal X-Ray diffraction data were recorded in a Bruker-AXS SMART APEX II X-Ray diffractometer. The cell refinement and data reduction was done using 'Bruker Saint'. Structure refinements and solutions were carried out in SHELXL-97 (Sheldrick, 1997) programme.

Typical procedure for synthesis of 2-[(2R,3S,4R)-3,4-bis(benzyloxy)-2-(benzyloxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran-5-yl]-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (3a):

To a round bottom flask **1a** (100.00 mg, 0.225 mmol, 1.0 equiv.), **2a** (36.49 mg, 0.338 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) dry CH₃CN (4 mL) and anhydrous FeCl₃ (7.29 mg, 0.045 mmol, 0.2 equiv.) were added sequentially, and then the reaction mixture was refluxed for a certain period (6 h, as monitored by TLC) of time under aerial O₂. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was evaporated under vacuum, and the residue was

diluted with CH₂Cl₂. It was washed with aqueous NaHCO₃ solution, and the aqueous layer was further extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 times). The combined organic layer was washed with H₂O and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was removed under rotary evaporator to afford a crude product, which was purified by column chromatography on silica gel using EtOAc-pet. ether (16:84, v/v) as eluent to give the pure product (**3a**, 108 mg) as a white solid in 90% yield. The spectroscopic data and X-ray crystallographic data are in good agreement with the product structure. The same procedure was applied for all the glycol fused chiral benzimidazoles (**3**) (Table 1).

2-[(2R,3S,4R)-3,4-Bis(benzyloxy)-2-(benzyloxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran-5-yl]-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (3a):

White solid; m.p. 110°C; [α]_D²⁵ + 93.7 (c 0.33, CHCl₃); IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹): 3417, 3030, 2863, 1665, 1632, 1583, 1517, 1294, 1190, 1097; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz, δ ppm): 3.83 (dd, 1H, *J* 4.2 Hz and 10.7 Hz), 3.91 (dd, 1H, *J* 5.2 Hz and 10.6 Hz), 4.20–4.24 (m, 1H), 4.39–4.44 (m, 1H), 4.50 (d, 1H, *J* 11.4 Hz), 4.60–4.63 (m, 3H), 4.67 (d, 1H, *J* 11.4 Hz), 4.78 (s, 2H), 7.15–7.16 (m, 2H), 7.28–7.29 (m, 2H), 7.32–7.35 (m, 10H), 7.39–7.40 (m, 2H), 7.41–7.42 (m, 3H), 7.77 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz, δ ppm): 67.8, 70.6, 71.9, 72.7, 73.3, 73.6, 76.9, 104.0, 122.1, 127.8, 128.0, 128.1, 128.5, 128.55, 128.6, 128.7, 129.0, 137.3, 137.7, 137.8, 149.2, 150.5; ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for C₃₄H₃₃N₂O₄ [M+H]⁺: 533.2440, Found: 533.2440.

2-[(2R,3S,4R)-3,4-Bis(benzyloxy)-2-(benzyloxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran-5-yl]-5-chloro-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (3d):

Brown syrup; [α]_D²⁵ + 64.6 (c 3.1, CHCl₃); IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹): 3399, 3029, 2865, 1680, 1645, 1570, 1529, 1288, 1189, 1094, 767; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz, δ ppm): 3.82 (dd, 1H, *J* 4.3 Hz and 10.8 Hz), 3.90 (dd, 1H, *J* 5.3 Hz and 10.7 Hz), 4.20 (t, 1H, *J* 5.3 Hz), 4.40–4.50 (m, 2H), 4.57–4.59 (m, 3H), 4.67 (d, 1H, *J* 11.5 Hz), 4.77 (s, 2H), 7.10 (d, 1H, *J* 8.2 Hz), 7.26–7.30 (m, 3H), 7.33–7.34 (m, 10H), 7.39–7.43 (m, 4H), 7.76 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz, δ ppm): 67.7, 70.7, 71.7, 72.6, 72.8, 73.5, 103.7, 122.5, 127.5, 127.8, 127.9, 128.1, 128.5, 128.6, 128.7, 129.0, 137.2, 137.5, 137.7, 149.5, 151.7; ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for C₃₄H₃₂ClN₂O₄ [M+H]⁺: 567.2051, Found: 567.2055.

2-[(2*R*,3*S*,4*R*)-3,4-Bis(benzyloxy)-2-(benzyloxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran-5-yl]-6-nitro-1*H*-benzo[d]imidazole (**3e**):

Dark yellow syrup; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 29.5$ (c 2.6, CHCl₃); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 3380, 3089, 3068, 3033, 2924, 2868, 1642, 1519, 1339, 1209, 1094; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, δ ppm): 3.79 (dd, 1H, *J* 4.6 Hz and 10.6 Hz, C₆'-H'), 3.87 (dd, 1H, *J* 5.6 Hz and 10.8 Hz, C₆'-H''), 4.19 (app. t, 1H, *J* 4.4 Hz, 4.8 Hz, C₄'-H), 4.50 (m, 3H, C₅'-H and C₆'-OCH₂Ph), 4.60 (d, *J* 11.2 Hz, 1H, C₃'-H), 4.67–4.74 (m, 4H, C₃'-OCH₂Ph and C₄'-OCH₂Ph), 7.23–7.42 (m, 16H, OCH₂Ph and C₄-H), 8.01 (s, 1H, C₁'-H), 8.04 (dd, 1H, *J* 1.8 Hz, 9.0 Hz, C₅-H), 8.22 (s, 1H, C₇-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz, δ ppm): 67.6 (C₆'), 71.1 (-OCH₂Ph), 71.3 (C₄'), 71.9 (C₃'), 72.7(-OCH₂Ph), 73.7 (-OCH₂Ph), 77.1 (C₅'), 102.5 (C₂'), 118.8 (C₅), 128.1 (C₄), 128.4–129.2 (-OCH₂Ph), 137.2 (C₇), 137.4 (C_{7a}), 137.6 (C_{3a}), 143.6 (C₆), 152.6 (C₁'), 154.7 (C₂); ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for C₃₄H₃₂N₃O₆ [M+H]⁺: 578.2291, Found: 578.2286.

[2-[(2*R*,3*S*,4*R*)-3,4-Bis(benzyloxy)-2-(benzyloxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran-5-yl]-1*H*-benzo[d]imidazol-6-yl]-phenylmethanone (**3f**):

White foamy solid; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 43.2$ (c 0.37, CHCl₃); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 3386, 3262, 3029, 2923, 2852, 1644, 1613, 1453, 1296, 1190, 1069; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz, δ ppm): 3.83 (dd, 1H, *J* 4.3 Hz and 10.7 Hz), 3.91 (dd, *J* 5.3 Hz, 10.7 Hz, 1H), 4.22 (t, *J* 5.2 Hz, 1H), 4.44–4.50 (m, 2H), 4.57–4.60 (m, 3H), 4.66–4.70 (m, 1H), 4.77 (s, 2H), 7.27–7.30 (m, 3H), 7.31–7.36 (m, 10H), 7.38–7.39 (m, 3H), 7.46–7.51 (m, 3H), 7.56–7.61 (m, 2H), 7.72 (d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.77–7.80 (m, 1H), 7.84 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz, δ ppm): 67.7, 70.8, 71.7, 72.6, 72.7, 73.6, 103.7, 124.8, 127.8, 127.9, 128.0, 128.12, 128.14, 128.5, 128.6, 128.8, 129.1, 129.9, 131.5, 131.8, 137.2, 137.5, 137.7, 138.6, 150.2, 196.7; ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for C₄₁H₃₇N₂O₅ [M+H]⁺: 637.2702, Found: 637.2734.

2-[(2*R*,3*S*,4*R*)-3,4-Dimethoxy-2-(methoxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran-5-yl]-5,6-dimethyl-1*H*-benzo[d]imidazole (**3i**):

Brown syrup; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 3.44$ (c 2.8, CHCl₃); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 3409, 3056, 2982, 2957, 2851, 1701, 1645, 1450, 1305, 1271, 1081; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz, δ ppm): 2.31 (s, 6H), 3.40 (s, 3H), 3.50 (s, 3H), 3.57 (s, 3H), 3.65 (dd, 1H, *J* 2.1 Hz, 6.3 Hz), 3.72 (dd, 1H, *J* 3.3 Hz, 6.6 Hz), 3.85 (t, 1H, *J* 3.5 Hz), 4.19–4.21 (m, 1H), 4.59 (d, 1H, *J* 3.0 Hz), 7.34 (s, 2H), 7.78 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz, δ ppm): 20.4,

55.3, 58.7, 59.2, 70.1, 72.9, 74.3, 103.4, 114.5, 132.2, 135.3, 149.4, 150.2; ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₄N₂O₄Na [M+Na]⁺: 355.1634, Found: 355.1632.

5-Chloro-2-[(2*R*,3*S*,4*R*)-3,4-dimethoxy-2-(methoxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran-5-yl]-1*H*-benzo[d]imidazole (**3j**):

Light brown syrup; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 18.2$ (c 1.4, CHCl₃); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 3051, 2932, 2831, 1647, 1454, 1429, 1281, 1178, 1089; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, δ ppm): 3.39 (s, 3H, C₆'-OMe), 3.47 (s, 3H, C₃'-OMe), 3.54 (s, 3H, C₄'-OMe), 3.63 (dd, 1H, *J* 3.6 Hz and 10.4 Hz, C₆'-H'), 3.71 (dd, 1H, *J* 5.6 Hz and 10.4 Hz, C₆'-H''), 3.83 (app. t, 1H, *J* 4.8 Hz, 6.4 Hz, C₄'-H), 4.20 (dd, 1H, *J* 5.2 Hz and 9.4 Hz, C'-H), 4.50 (d, 1H, *J* 3.9 Hz, C₃'-H), 7.13 (dd, 1H, *J* 1.8 Hz and 8.2 Hz, C₆-H), 7.40 (d, 1H, *J* 8.8 Hz, C₇-H), 7.48 (d, 1H, *J* 1.6 Hz, C₄-H), 7.65 (s, 1H, C₁'-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 Mz, δ ppm): 55.1 (C₃'-OMe), 58.8 (C₄'-OMe), 59.2 (C₆'-OMe), 70.0 (C₆'), 73.1 (C₄'), 75.1 (C₃'), 77.0 (C₅'), 103.9 (C₂'), 114.5 (C₇), 115.2 (C₄), 122.9 (C₆), 127.9 (C₅), 136.9 (C_{7a}), 139.2 (C_{3a}), 150.0 (C₁'), 151.8 (C₂); ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for C₁₆H₂₀ClN₂O₄ [M+H]⁺: 339.1112, Found: 339.1107.

2-[(2*R*,3*S*,4*R*)-3,4-Dimethoxy-2-(methoxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran-5-yl]-6-nitro-1*H*-benzo[d]imidazole (**3k**):

Yellow syrup; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 9.1$ (c 1.2, CHCl₃); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 3055, 2979, 2839, 1644, 1560, 1454, 1432, 1287, 1182, 1092; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz, δ ppm): 3.4 3 (s, 3H), 3.55 (s, 3H), 3.59 (s, 3H), 3.69 (dd, *J* 3.3 Hz and 10.8 Hz, 1H), 3.77 (dd, *J* 4.9 Hz, 10.8 Hz, 1H), 3.89 (t, *J* 12.5 Hz, 1H), 4.20–4.24 (m, 1H), 4.53 (d, 1H, *J* 5.3 Hz), 7.55 (d, 1H, *J* 8.9 Hz), 7.78 (s, 1H), 8.13 (dd, 1H, *J* 2.1 Hz and 8.8 Hz), 8.43 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz, δ ppm): 55.1, 58.8, 59.2, 69.8, 73.0, 75.3, 103.4, 118.4, 143.3, 151.4, 155.1; ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₉N₃O₆Na [M+Na]⁺: 372.1172, Found: 372.1172.

2-[(2*R*,3*R*,4*R*)-3,4-Bis(benzyloxy)-2-(benzyloxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran-5-yl]-5,6-dimethyl-1*H*-benzo[d]imidazole (**3n**):

Brown syrup; $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 24.3$ (c 2.28, CHCl₃); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 3400, 3030, 2922, 2858, 1638, 1454, 1307, 1182, 1090, 1027; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz, δ ppm): 2.31 (s, 6H), 3.88–3.92 (m, 2H), 4.21 (bs, 1H), 4.46–4.59 (m, 3H), 4.65–4.71 (m, 3H), 4.85–4.91 (dd, 2H, *J* 8.2 Hz and 10.2 Hz), 7.14 (bs, 2H), 7.34–7.41 (m, 14H), 7.50 (s, 1H, C₁'-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz, δ ppm): 20.3, 29.6, 67.7, 71.7,

71.8, 73.1, 73.2, 73.5, 76.1, 104.7, 127.7, 127.9, 128.2, 128.3, 128.4, 128.5, 128.8, 130.8, 137.6, 137.8, 147.6, 149.9; ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{37}N_2O_4$ $[M+H]^+$: 561.2753, Found: 561.2734.

2-[(2R,3R,4R)-3,4-Bis(benzyloxy)-2-(benzyloxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran-5-yl]-6-nitro-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (**3o**):

Yellow syrup; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +104.4$ (c 1.9, $CHCl_3$); IR (KBr, ν_{max}/cm^{-1}): 3375, 3088, 3063, 3030, 2921, 2866, 1640, 1516, 1338, 1207, 1091; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz, δ): 3.79–3.80 (m, 2H), 4.18 (s, 1H), 4.37 (s, 1H), 4.42 (d, 1H, J 6.9 Hz), 4.49 (d, 1H, J 6.9 Hz), 4.58 (d, 1H, J 6.9 Hz), 4.68 (d, 2H, J 6.9 Hz), 4.81 (m, 2H), 7.17 (s, 1H), 7.23–7.32 (m, 12H), 7.39–7.40 (m, 3H), 7.65 (s, 1H), 8.00 (d, 1H, J 6.9 Hz), 8.10 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$, 75 MHz, δ): 67.7, 70.7, 72.6, 73.2, 73.8, 74.1, 103.7, 118.3, 128.0, 128.1, 128.2, 128.66, 128.68, 129.1, 129.4, 137.2, 137.7, 137.8, 143.2, 150.7; ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for $C_{34}H_{32}N_3O_6$ $[M+H]^+$: 578.2291, Found: 578.2286.

2-[(2R,3R,4R)-3,4-Dimethoxy-2-(methoxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran-5-yl]-1H-anthra[1,2-d]imidazole-6,11-dione (**3r**):

Orange solid; m.p. 236°C; IR (KBr, ν_{max}/cm^{-1}): 3440, 3079, 2920, 2842, 1730, 1631, 1570, 1442, 1280, 1186, 1050; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 400 MHz, δ ppm): 3.46 (s, 3H, C_6' -OMe), 3.70 (s, 3H, C_4' -OMe), 3.76 (d, 2H, J 6.4 Hz, C_6' -H'H"), 3.87 (s, 3H, C_3' -OMe), 4.03 (app. t, 1H, J 1.2 Hz and 2.0 Hz, C_4' -H), 4.35 (t, 1H, J 6.4 Hz, C_5' -H), 4.60 (d, 1H, J 2.4 Hz, C_3' -H), 7.72–7.78 (m, 2H, C_8 -H and C_9 -H), 7.86 (s, 1H, C_1' -H), 7.93 (d, 1H, J 8.4 Hz, C_4 -H), 8.15 (d, 1H, J 8.4 Hz, C_5 -H), 8.23 (dd, 1H, J 2.0 Hz and 5.6 Hz, C_7), 8.28 (dd, 1H, J 1.6 Hz and 7.2 Hz, C_{10} -H), 11.58 (s, 1H, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$, 100 MHz, δ ppm): 58.1 (C_3' -OMe), 59.4 (C_6' -OMe), 60.8 (C_4' -OMe), 70.0 (C_6'), 71.2 (C_4'), 74.9 (C_3'), 77.3 (C_5'), 103.4 (C_2'), 117.6 (C_{11a}), 122.1 (C_5), 123.8 (C_4), 126.5 (C_7), 127.6 (C_{5a}), 127.7 (C_{10}), 132.3 (C_{11b}), 133.4 (C_{10a}), 133.7 (C_8), 134.1 (C_{6a}), 134.3 (C_9), 148.2 (C_{3a}), 151.5 (C_2'), 156.5 (C_2), 182.7 (C_{11}), 184.9 (C_6); ESI-HR-MS Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{23}N_2O_6$ $[M+H]^+$: 435.1556, Found 435.1550.

Antimicrobial activity:

Microorganisms for study: A total of ten microbial cultures, comprising eight bacterial and two fungal strains, were collected from superficial and subcutaneous infections for this study. All the bacterial and fungal isolates, including MSSA

(methicillin sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus*), MRSA (methicillin resistance *S. aureus*), and ESBL (extended spectrum β -lactamase) – producer strains, were characterized by standard laboratory protocol^{21–23}.

Bacterial strains: Seven synthesized benzimidazole derivatives (**3a**, **3c**, **3g**, **3l**, **3n**, **3o**, **3r**) were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at a concentration of 4 mg/mL, and screened for antibacterial activity by the agar well diffusion assay¹⁸. The bacterial culture in Muller Hinton broth (MHB) was adjusted to the final inoculum density of 1×10^7 cfu/mL (by 0.5 McFarland standard) on molten Muller Hinton agar (MHA) plates. After solidification, wells (diameter 5 mm) were made with a sterile borer in the inoculated MHA plates. 50 μ L solution containing 0.2 mg of each compound was dispensed in each well, while DMSO was also tested as the vehicle control. Ciprofloxacin and gentamicin were the standard drugs used as positive controls in this assay. Antibacterial activity was expressed as the diameters of inhibition zones produced by the antimicrobials, and measured after 24 h of incubation at 37°C.

Fungal strains: The selected benzimidazole derivatives were screened for antifungal activity¹⁸. Fungal culture in Sabouraud Dextrose broth (SDB) containing an inoculum density of 0.5 McFarland (1×10^8 cfu/mL) was diluted at 1:10 ratio in SDA plate to obtain the final inoculum concentration of 1×10^7 cfu/mL. Wells (diameter 5 mm) were punched on solidified SDA plates and 50 μ L solution containing 0.2 mg of each compound was dispensed in each well, and DMSO was tested as the vehicle control. Fluconazole (0.02 mg/well; dissolved in DMSO) was used alone as a standard antifungal agent. The diameter of the inhibition zone was measured after 24 h of incubation at 35°C. Antifungal activity was expressed as diameters of inhibition zones around the wells produced by the tested compounds and antifungal agent.

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC):

Bacterial strains: The MIC of the benzimidazole derivatives against the tested bacteria was determined by broth micro-dilution procedure to find the lowest concentration of the extract at which no growth was visible. Stock solutions (1.024 mg/mL) of seven benzimidazole derivatives were prepared in DMSO, and serially diluted in MHB at concentrations of 512, 256, 128, 64, 32, 16, 8 and 4 μ g/mL in a 96-well microtitre plate. The broth culture containing 0.5 McFarland (1×10^8 cfu/mL) inoculum density was then introduced to each

of the microtitre wells at 1:10 ratio to maintain final inoculum density of 1×10^7 cfu/mL. Microtitre plates were incubated for 18 h at 37°C, and the presence of visible growth in each well was inferred by measuring OD at 630 nm using ELISA reader (Erba LisaScan II, Transasia)^{18,21}.

Fungal strains: MIC for benzimidazole derivatives against the fungal isolates was determined in a similar procedure, using SDB in 96-well microtitre plates incubated for 18 h at 35°C²⁴. The presence of visible growth was determined spectrophotometrically as above.

Determination of drug resistance profile of the isolated bacteria: Antibacterial susceptibility studies were carried out by Kirby and Bauer disk diffusion technique using commercially available antibiotic disks. Bacterial culture in peptone water (Hi-Media, India) containing 0.5 McFarland turbidity (1×10^8 cfu/mL) was swabbed in MHA plate. Antibiotic disks were placed on it by maintaining about 20 mm distance with each other^{21,25}. Inhibition zone diameter was measured after overnight incubation at 37°C and results were interpreted as per CLSI guidelines²¹.

Evaluation of benzimidazole derivative induced DNA damage in *Candida tropicalis* by-alkaline single cell gel electrophoresis (SCGE, or Comet assay): *Candida tropicalis* cell suspension at 0.5 McFarland ($\sim 1 \times 10^8$ Cells/ml) was diluted in nuclease free water (to prepare negative control), 100 μ M H₂O₂ solution (to prepare positive control), **3n** and **3r** (200 μ g/mL) solution at a ratio of 1:10 (v/v) and kept for 30 min at 4°C. After that, aliquots from negative control, positive control, **3n** and **3r** treated samples were further diluted in phosphate buffered saline (PBS; Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ free; pH 7.4) at a ratio of 1:100 (v/v) to attain final cell density 1×10^5 /mL. SCGE was performed using comet assay reagent kit (Trivigen, Gaithersburg, MD, catalog # 4250-050-K) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, *C. tropicalis* cell suspension (1×10^5 cells/ml) in PBS was combined with 1% molten low melting agarose (Catalog # 4250-050-02) at 37°C at a ratio of 1:10 (v/v) and transferred to comet slide (Catalog # 4250-050-03). After gelling time (~ 30 min), the slide was immersed respectively, in pre-chilled (4°C) lysis solution (Catalog # 4250-050-01) and alkaline solution (200 mM NaOH, 1 mM EDTA, pH > 13) for 45 min in each. Then electrophoresis of slide was conducted in pre-chilled (4°C) alkaline electrophoresis²⁶ solution (200 mM NaOH, 1 mM EDTA, pH > 13) for 30 min at 25 volt and 300 mA (1.5 V/cm), and then

washed in deionized water, dehydrated in 70% ethanol and stained with SYBR[®] Green I (Catalog # 4250-050-05, maximum excitation/emission was 494 nm/521 nm) diluted in TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 1 mM EDTA)²⁷. Fluorescent comet patterns were examined with a MOTIC BA400 microscope under 200 \times magnification and fluoro-isothiocyanate (FITC) filter combination and images captured by a charge-couple device (CCD) camera.

Image analysis: Comet Score Freeware v1.5 (TriTek Corporation) was used to measure comet length (number of pixels in the horizontal direction of the comet), Comet Height (pixels in the vertical direction of the comet), Comet Area (number of pixels in the comet), Comet Intensity (sum of all pixel intensity values in the comet), Comet Mean Intensity (average of all pixel intensity values in the comet), Head Diameter (number of pixels in horizontal direction of the comet head), Head Area (number of pixels in comet head), Head Mean Intensity (average of all pixel intensity values in the comet head), %DNA in Head (total comet head intensity divided by the total comet intensity, multiplied by 100), Tail Length (comet head diameter subtracted from the overall comet length), Tail Area (number of pixels in the comet tail), Tail Intensity (sum of all pixel intensity values in comet tail), %DNA in Tail (total comet tail intensity divided by the total comet intensity, multiplied by 100), Tail Moment (%DNA in the comet tail multiplied by the tail length), and Olive Moment²⁸ (summation of each tail intensity integral value, multiplied by its relative distance from the center of the head and divided by the total comet intensity)²⁷, Hundred cells per sample were observed using this software.

Results were expressed as means \pm SE and statistical comparison of results with negative control sample value, were performed by independent, two tailed, Student's t-test. Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$. Comparison of tail length, tail intensity, %DNA in tail and tail moment within different samples was depicted using box-whisker plot (done by Microsoft Excel 2002 statistical software).

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